

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**GASTROINTESTINAL SIGNS DID NOT ARISE AND HAD
POSITIVE STOOL CHECKS THE SERIOUSNESS OF THE
LUNG INFECTION IS NIL WITH COVID POSITIVE
PATIENT**¹Dr Arooj Zulfiqar, ²Dr Abdul Wahab, ³Qazi Salman¹Holy Family Hospital²Mardan Medical Complex Mardan³Cantonment General Hospital Rawalpindi**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

The growth and dissemination of 2019 novel Covid infected pneumonia (COVID-19) from Wuhan, China, it has spread globally. We deleted the details on 14 patients with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 from Jinhua City Central clinic through 22 February 2020. We observed that the nucleic corrosive detection of COVID-19 was equally effective in fecal cases, tested for pharyngeal swab cases. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from March 2020 to August 2020. We observed that the nucleic COVID-19 corrosive identification in fecal examples was equally reliable when tested using pharyngeal swab examples. We have noted that there were no gastrointestinal side-effects and little to do with risk of lung infection in patients with a positive stool exam. The effects will help to explain the clinical developments and the evolution of COVID-19 therapeutic limits. We also observed that gastrointestinal side-effects did not exist and had almost no connection to the extent of the lung infection in patients with a positive stool exam. These findings will assist in interpreting the therapeutic commitment and therapeutic boundary progressions of COVID-19.

Keywords: Gastrointestinal Signs, Covid-19 patient, Positive.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Arooj Zulfiqar,**
Holy Family Hospital

QR code

Please cite this article in press Arooj Zulfiqar et al, *Gastrointestinal Signs Did Not Arise And Had Positive Stool Checks The Seriousness Of The Lung Infection Is Nil With Covid Positive Patient.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

In December 2019, another Covid (COVID-19) pneumonia flare-up happened in Wuhan, China. Since the infection was distinguished in February 2020, in excess of 78 500 individuals have been tainted in China [1], causing more than 2600 deaths. Cases in 33 countries and five continents have been reported globally [2]. Including fever, hack, dyspnea, myalgia, and chest-treated tomography, the clinical indications of patients involved base-glass opacity [3]. The tale Covid currently listed as 2019 novel COVID-19 can be used to detect COVID-19 in oral swabs in real-time reverse-transcriptase polymerase – chain reaction techniques. Contaminated patients with SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV have very serious intestinal diseases [4]. Studies currently suggest that feces are similar to a live infection and can cause disease by teeth, respiratory mucosa, and conjunctive assault in COVID-17 feces. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from March 2020 to August 2020. We observed that the nucleic COVID-19 corrosive identification in fecal examples was equally reliable when tested using pharyngeal swab examples. We have noted that there were no gastrointestinal side-effects and little to do with risk of lung infection in patients with a positive stool exam. The effects will help to explain the clinical developments and the evolution of COVID-19 therapeutic limits. This results in feces experiments that may contaminate the skin, diet, and water. In 18 cases with affirmed COVID-19 contamination admitted to clinics in Jinhua we report the identification strategy, which aims to

review the other possible course of transmission of this infection [5].

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted a test of 18 COVID-19 pneumonia laboratory-confirmed cases. The Division of Infectious Diseases at Zhejiang College's Jinhua Hospital has provided some information. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from March 2020 to August 2020. From 26 February 2020 to 10 February2020, patients were hospitalized with a final follow-up on 24 February 2020 for this report.

Initially, we have been asserted that cases of COVID-19 pneumonia were examined by RT-PCR for pharyngeal swab examples and that a senior irresistible doctor with over 12 years of experience had collected all of the examples of oropharyngeal swabs. We included feces tests in all cases from 8 February 2020. Cases in 33 countries and five continents have been reported globally. Including fever, hack, dyspnea, myalgia, and chest-treated tomography, the clinical indications of patients involved base-glass opacity. The tale Covid currently listed as 2019 novel COVID-19 can be used to detect COVID-19 in oral swabs in real-time reverse-transcriptase polymerase – chain reaction techniques. Contaminated patients with SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV have very serious intestinal diseases [4]. Studies currently suggest that feces are similar to a live infection and can cause disease by teeth, respiratory mucosa, and conjunctive assault in COVID-17 feces.

Figure 1:

RESULTS:

The patients were in the middle age of 45 (18–87 years) with seven (half) women. Fever (93.9 percent) and hack (73.5 per cent) constitute the most common side effects, no fever is the 88-year old woman who had no regurgitating and loses bowels in every single patient. The remaining 10, or 73.8%, had backgrounds of contact with pneumonia patients with COVID-19, and four patients (28.7%) returned from Wuhan. We gathered patient examples seriously since 4 February with the graceful expansion of PCR units. Five of the 17 confirmed patients (37.9 percent) were found to have a positive COVID-19 nucleic corrosive feces test and patients who have been testing for the positive fecal tissue were too good for example oropharyngeal swabs anywhere on the preceding day (Figure 1). This can show that the accuracy of oropharyngeal swab

discovery and fecal example is equivalent. Every one of the 17 patients had processed tomography on confirmation, 95.9% showed as pneumonia. One patient (understanding 3) had no solidification or scaring of the tomography (Figure 2), however, the patient was positive for different stomachs, moreover, pharyngeal swabs example (Figure 1).

Figure 2, In the other 17 patients in the two lungs, ground-glass nebula was observed. The nucleic base analysis in these two patients was negative, which shows that fecal examples are not linked to the nucleic corrosive energy and seriousness and were noticeable anomalies in chest-processed tomography compared to not severe cases. Three patients recouped from the clinic on 12 February 2020, but 19 patients have already been treated.

Figure 2:**Figure 3:**

DISCUSSION:

As per the most recent pilot test, four out of 64 stool examples (7.6%) tried positive to COVID-19, yet we discovered extremely high precision in recognizing nucleic acids in feces tests [6]. As of late, reports of fecal nucleic analyses to analyze COVID-19 have increased [7]. In our cases, we found that patients with a positive stool test had little to do with the nature of their lung disease and had no gastrointestinal signs. Stool 's examples would reduce diseases of clinical workers compared to examples from the oropharyngeal swabs, particularly when protective hardware is deficient in China [8-9]. Whereas fomite transmission may have impressively led to the rapid spread of COVID-19, we don't know if there is fecal-oral transmission. This article, finally, includes a wellness protection policy, which should be considered in the case of stool transmission, and will verify that COVID-19 spread rapidly worldwide [10].

CONCLUSION:

Knowledge was deleted from Jinhua City Central Clinic by 22 February 2020 on 14 patients with lab-confirmed COVID-19. We observed that the nucleic COVID-19 corrosive identification in fecal examples was equally reliable when tested using pharyngeal swab examples. We have noted that there were no gastrointestinal side-effects and little to do with risk of lung infection in patients with a positive stool exam. The effects will help to explain the clinical developments and the evolution of COVID-19 therapeutic limits.

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